

Eviction from paradise: Lived experience, psycho-social and health effects of allotment garden loss

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ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Nadja Kabisch

Keywords:

Allotment gardens
Mental health
Well-being
Social networks
Eviction
Redevelopment
Mixed methods
Natural experiment

ABSTRACT

This mixed-methods paper examines the experience and effects of the loss of an allotment garden among gardeners in Zurich, Switzerland. The paper explores the subjective experience of garden loss using qualitative material gathered in field conversations with gardeners from an allotment area which was soon to be cleared for construction. In parallel, gardeners from the same area were surveyed before (2018) and after (2019) the clearance, thus constructing a natural experiment to measure effects on gardeners' social networks, social support and general and mental health.

The analysis of the qualitative material shows the (imminent) loss of the garden was a distressing experience for most participants, a result which is strongly supported by the descriptive analysis of several survey questions. Analysis of the quantitative data with ANCOVA models gives support to a negative effect of garden loss on the number of social contacts and on emotional well-being, but not on other factors.

The experience of garden loss shows strong parallels to that of loss of a home, but also differs from it in relevant ways. Improved designs of similar natural experiments could lead to more reliable results. These would, however, require researchers to observe planning processes from a very early stage.

1. Introduction

In garden [number] a woman starts talking to us, invites us into her garden and offers us grapes. "This is my paradise" she says. Fieldnotes 19.8.2019.

1.1. Loss of an allotment garden

With the number of people living in urban areas set to reach 70% by the middle of the century (United Nations, 2019), urban greenspaces are becoming increasingly important for the quality of life and health of the world's population. Allotment gardens are a form of private urban greenspace which is widespread across Europe (Bell and Fox-Kämper, 2016). Often called "family gardens" in Switzerland, they are accessible to people with limited financial means and in Swiss cities (still) serve a relatively under-privileged population. Allotment gardens are, however, under pressure from development in Swiss cities, as elsewhere in Europe (Haaland and Van den Bosch, 2015). Allotment garden areas which often contain hundreds of adjacent gardens of around 100 m² each represent considerable land reserves in parts of cities which have become increasingly central as these cities have grown. In many larger

Swiss cities, allotment garden areas have been or are planned to be closed, cleared and used for construction projects.

Allotment gardens and urban greenspaces more generally have positive effects on health and restoration (Frumkin et al., 2017; Tzoulas et al., 2007; Hartig, 2004) as well as on social networks and social capital (Christensen et al., 2019; Nordh et al., 2016; Kingsley and Townsend, 2006). On the other hand, being evicted from a home has been shown to have considerable negative effects on somatic and mental health. Thus, losing access to allotment gardens could be expected to have negative psycho-social effects on garden users. In this article we ask what happens when allotment gardeners lose their "paradise". We explore how allotment garden users evicted from their gardens experience the loss of the garden and what effects garden loss may have on garden users' social networks and health.

1.2. Well-being and health effects of contact to nature and gardening

Our understanding of health in this paper aligns with the World Health Organisation's (WHO) concept of health as a "state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity." (WHO, 2012:2). We thus view mental health as a

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“state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community.” (WHO, 2012:1). Contact to nature is shown to have beneficial effects on physical and mental health of humans by a large body of research (for reviews see Frumkin et al., 2017, Tzoulas et al., 2007, Health Council of the Netherlands, 2004).

Walking in a natural environment can lead to increased subjective well-being (Martens et al., 2011). Exposure to greenspace is shown to be related to better recovery from stress and more positive emotions as well as to attention restoration (Van den Berg et al., 2014; Hartig et al., 2003). A higher proportion of green space close to the home is related to lower prevalence of many diseases, particularly anxiety disorders and depression (Maas et al., 2009). There is evidence that moving home from a less green urban area to a greener area has sustained positive effects on mental health (Alcock et al., 2014). The negative effects of socio-economic inequalities on health may also be attenuated by a greater availability of greenspace (Mitchell and Popham, 2008).

Gardening, as a particular form of contact to nature, has repeatedly been shown to improve physical and mental health (Soga et al., 2017b offer a review). In descriptive studies, gardeners (we use the term ‘gardener’ throughout to refer to garden users, not to professional gardeners) report perceived mental health benefits and describe the garden as a place of relaxation and escape from work or everyday problems (Freeman et al., 2012; Gross and Lane, 2007). Van den Berg and Custers (2011) show that short-term stress (measured by salivary cortisol levels and self-reporting) is reduced significantly more by a gardening activity than by a control activity such as recreational reading in the garden.

Further studies provide evidence specifically that gardening in allotments has beneficial effects on psychological restoration and health (Young et al., 2020; Hofmann et al., 2018; Clatworthy et al., 2017; Soga et al., 2017a; Wood et al., 2016; Van den Berg et al., 2010). Allotment gardening is related to positive health effects for older people, which has been explained by the social contacts and the social support the garden fosters (Van den Berg et al., 2010; Milligan et al., 2004). Evidence for social support functioning as a protective factor against depression has been presented repeatedly (Rueger et al., 2016). Allotment gardens also facilitate the generation of social capital and social networks in some settings (Nordh et al., 2016; Delshammar et al., 2016; Cabannes and Raposo, 2013; Glover, 2004). Social contacts, well-being and escaping loneliness are motivations for and benefits of gardening in allotment gardens (Lewis et al., 2018; Clatworthy et al., 2017; Nordh et al., 2016; Frauenfelder et al., 2015; Milligan et al., 2004), while allotments are also an important space for activities in a family context and provide a meaningful form of leisure activity (Frauenfelder et al., 2015; Gross and Lane, 2007).

1.3. Well-being and health effects of loss of a home

As far as we know, there is no research on the psycho-social effects of allotment garden loss. However, there is a body of research on the psycho-social and health effects of different kinds of housing instability, e.g. evictions of residents from rented or owned homes. We discuss this research as a background to our study, as we assume that effects and mechanisms of loss of a home and loss of a garden will be similar. Review articles (Vásquez-Vera et al., 2017; Tsai, 2015) show that many studies identified an association between negative mental, general and physical health outcomes with the fact of being at risk of eviction (either as a tenant or a homeowner), having suffered an eviction or living in an area with a high proportion of evictions or repossessions. Self-rated general health was significantly worse among homeowners affected by repossession or by renters evicted from their homes in the USA (Hoke and Boen, 2021; Cannuscio et al., 2012) and in Spain (Vásquez-Vera et al., 2016). Effects were stronger among people who had experienced eviction than among those who were at risk of eviction (Vásquez-Vera et al., 2016; Cannuscio et al., 2012).

Mental health has also been shown to be negatively related to housing instability. Individuals who had experienced repossession of their home were more likely to report poor mental health or serious psychological distress than the general population (Vásquez-Vera et al., 2016; Cannuscio et al., 2012). Similarly, renters behind on their rent were more likely to have symptoms of minor or major depression than other renters (Burgard et al., 2012). While these studies and many others on the topic are cross-sectional, a number of longitudinal studies provide more robust support of an effect of eviction or repossession on mental health (Hoke and Boen, 2021; McLaughlin et al., 2012; Pevalin, 2009). In most studies, the mechanism linking eviction and mental health is stress caused by eviction (Hoke and Boen, 2021; Tsai, 2015).

Forced moving or the loss of a home also has been shown to be related to social capital. The size of social networks and the frequency of neighborhood contacts were larger after relocation in some studies (Lawson et al., 2015; Kearns and Mason, 2013) but smaller in others (Huang et al., 2017; Clampet-Lundquist, 2010). The negative effect on social capital seems to be greater if relocation is involuntary and if individuals have a lower socio-economic status (Huang et al., 2017; Posthumus et al., 2014).

1.4. Aims and hypotheses

In the present study we combine aims related to a qualitative and a quantitative approach. First, we aimed to understand how users of allotment gardens experience the imminent loss of their garden due to the clearance of an allotment area. Second, we asked what effects in relation to social networks, general health, mental health and emotional well-being the loss of the garden had on gardeners. Regarding psychosocial effects, we hypothesized that the loss of the allotment garden would lead to:

1. ...a loss of social contacts of gardeners
2. ...a reduction in perceived social support
3. ...a deterioration of self-rated general health
4. ...a deterioration of mental health (broad measure)
5. ...a deterioration of emotional well-being (emotions focused measure)

2. Methods

2.1. Study overview

For this mixed-methods study we combined qualitative research with a quantitative quasi-experiment. We utilized the partial clearance of an allotment garden area to conduct a quasi-experiment with a treatment and a control group and measurement in two survey waves (referred to as t1 and t2) before and after the clearance of gardens. In parallel to the collection of this quantitative data, we gathered qualitative material (field notes and interviews) as described in Section 2.2.

The allotment garden area named *Vulkan* in the city of Zurich, Switzerland was partially cleared for the construction of an ice-hockey stadium at the end of 2018. The gardens were located on land owned by the city, which had leased it to the allotment garden association for decades, which in turn leased single allotments to gardeners. The allotment garden association is a self-organized entity which manages the allotment garden area, enforces rules etc. Until 2017 this land lay in a zoning area reserved for allotment garden use, which was changed to accommodate the construction project.

The allotment gardener association granted us permission to conduct the study. Permissions from the cantonal and national ethics commissions were not necessary, as is the rule for research of this kind under Swiss law. Participants were informed about the study at first contact and gave oral consent to participate in the study. All data was and is accessible only to the authors and temporarily to a research assistant. It is stored on internal servers of the Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL.

Quantitative and qualitative data was pseudonymized.

2.2. Collection of qualitative material

Qualitative material was collected as field notes and qualitative interviews. The principal investigator and one other interviewer took extensive field notes on encounters and conversations in the Vulkan allotment area during recruitment and surveying for the first wave of the survey (see 2.5 for more details on surveying). Field notes were written up from memory and from short notes after leaving the allotment area.

2.3. Qualitative sample

In the first wave we took field notes of 116 conversations, 66 of which were with people who were to lose their gardens, 50 with other gardeners. The field conversations took place with 71 different individuals in the allotment area; as we spoke to some people more than once, the number of recorded conversations is higher than the number of people participating. Of the 71 individuals, 25 also completed the quantitative questionnaire. The length of the conversations ranged from just a few minutes to 2 h. In the second wave, survey interviews were arranged in prior with the participants and far less time was spent in the field. In this wave we collected 18 short problem-centered qualitative interviews which were conducted with participants before and/or after completing the quantitative questionnaire.

2.4. Analysis of qualitative material

Qualitative analysis followed the thematic framework method (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003), which in turn utilizes many techniques from grounded theory analysis (Corbin, 2008). The material was coded (or labelled, cf. Ritchie and Lewis, 2003:224) in the software MAXQDA based on a coding scheme which was developed iteratively during analysis, using comparison and memo writing, leading to a descriptive analysis of experience.

2.5. Quantitative sampling and surveying

Two separate samples of allotment gardens were drawn at the beginning of the study for quantitative analysis: one from the set of allotment gardens earmarked for clearance (treatment sample), the other from the set of gardens which escaped destruction (control sample). As gardeners did (to our knowledge) not differ systematically in relation to the location of their garden in the allotment area, the clearing of the south-eastern third of the allotment area meant that gardeners who lost their gardens represented a random sample of all the gardeners in the area. Gardeners were interviewed face-to-face by interviewers using a quantitative questionnaire in 2018 (t1) and again in 2019 (t2).

In 2018 gardeners were recruited for the study by four interviewers who visited the allotment garden area repeatedly on different weekdays and at different times. The interviewers addressed gardeners in their allotments and conducted the survey either on the spot or at an arranged later time. Only one gardener per allotment was permitted to participate. Surveys were conducted in German (the local language) or Italian (as many gardeners speak Italian as a first or second language).

2.6. Quantitative sample

The control and treatment samples were drawn separately. For the control sample, 62 gardens were randomly selected from a map of the 185 gardens which were not threatened by the construction project. Interviewers visited these 62 gardens, addressed gardeners where present and completed a total of 32 interviews of which three were excluded for various reasons (see Table 1). This resulted in 29 valid cases in the control sample corresponding to a response rate of 47% (see Table 2). Originally the plan was to draw the treatment sample in the

Table 1
Quantitative sample in wave 1 (2018).

Total cases	65
Exclusion due to:	
Language problems	1
Interview not completed	3
Interview not assignable to group or garden	3
Total valid cases	58

Table 2
Quantitative sample in waves 1 + 2.

	Wave 1 (2018, t1)		Wave 2 (2019, t2)	
	Total Cases	Response rate	Total cases	Survival rate
Treatment group	29	–	20	69%
Control group	29	47%	25	86%

same way, but this had to be revised during the first weeks of field work in 2018. As many gardeners in the clearance area had already abandoned their gardens and were never present, it proved impossible to reach a sufficiently large sample using random sampling. Instead, interviewers addressed any gardener they met in the treatment area, making the treatment sample a convenience sample. For this sample, 33 interviews were conducted, after exclusion 29 valid cases (out of 123 gardens) remained. The total quantitative sample was thus 58 with two groups of equal size. Of these, 11 interviews were conducted in Italian, 47 in German.

Gardeners who had lost their garden in 2018 were contacted in 2019 by letter, email or telephone and surveyed in a place of their choice. Gardeners whose allotment was not destroyed were contacted on site in the garden for the second survey in 2019. In the treatment group 20 respondents participated a second time, in the control group the number was 25 (see Table 2). A total of ten gardeners in the treatment group had moved to a new allotment garden by t2. While they did not remain without a garden, they did experience eviction.

On most socio-economic dimensions, the groups were similar (see Table 3). The average age in the two groups was very similar at 54 years in the treatment and 56 years in the control group. In both groups 33% of participants were born in Switzerland. In the treatment group 44% were born in Southern Europe (control: 37%), 11% in South-Eastern Europe (control: 22%) and 7% outside of Europe (control: 7%). In the treatment group 31% had not finished school or only mandatory education (control: 27%), 45% had vocational training (control: 40%), 3% had attained upper secondary education (control: 7%) and 17% had a tertiary degree (control: 27%). The employment rate (more than 5 h of work a week) in the treatment group was 62% (control: 60%), while 24% of participants in the treatment group were retired (control: 30%). In the treatment group 21% of the participants were women, in the control group 37% were women.

Compared with the Swiss population (see Table 3), the total sample was older, more male, more likely to have migrated to Switzerland and to be socio-economically disadvantaged compared to the general Swiss

Table 3
Quantitative sample: socio-economic characteristics and comparison to the Swiss population.

	Treatment group	Control group	Swiss population
Average age (years)	54	56	42
Women	21%	37%	50%
Born outside Switzerland	67%	67%	30%
Mandatory or no education	31%	27%	19%
Tertiary education	17%	27%	35%
Employment rate	62%	60%	69%

population. This is comparable to other allotment gardens in Switzerland (see Young et al., 2020, Frauenfelder et al., 2015), but is also partly due to the underprivileged urban area the gardens are located in.

2.7. Measures in quantitative questionnaire

Beside questions regarding socio-demographics (age, gender, country of birth, educational attainment, current employment situation) the paper-and-pencil quantitative questionnaire used by the interviewers contained questions on experience of garden loss as well as variables to measure social contacts, social support and health (see Table 4).

The measures of numbers of close contacts with other allotment gardeners in the same allotment area and perceived support from these contacts are analogous to those in the Swiss household panel regarding neighbors (SHP 2018). A further measure of social support, the Berlin Social Support Scale (Schulz and Schwarzer, 2003), was included. Health measures were based on the well-established SF-12 and the SF-36 (Bullinger and Kirchberger, 1998). We measured self-rated general health with the single item-question from SF-12/SF-36. For a broad measure of mental health, we employed the mental health score from the SF-12 which includes the dimensions vitality, social functioning, role limitations due to emotional problems and mental well-being. As a more focused measure, we used the emotional well-being score from the SF-36 which covers depression, anxiety, and emotional control. For details on index calculation see Bullinger and Kirchberger (1998).

2.8. Analysis of quantitative data

Statistical analysis was done using R version 3.6.3 (R Core Team, 2020). For the variables used in the ANCOVA models we imputed missing data with multiple imputation using the R package mice (Buuren and Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011). Values at t2 were only imputed for participants who had responded at both t1 and t2. By imputing missing values rather than discarding cases with missing values we can exploit more of the information contained in the dataset. However, with 5 missing values (approx. 10%) the variable "mental health score at t2"

Table 4
Main measures in the quantitative questionnaire.

	number of items	scale of items
Measures of views on eviction		
Dis/agreement with statement: "I'm angry that allotment gardeners are being evicted because of the stadium."	1	5-point scale
Dis/agreement with statement: "It is right to build the stadium here."	1	5-point scale
Dis/agreement with statement: "Losing my garden means losing something important in my life."	1	5-point scale
Measures of social networks and support		
Number of close contacts with other allotment gardeners	1	6-point scale
Perceived practical and emotional support from other allotment gardeners	2	10-point scale
Berlin Social Support scale	8	4-point scale
Example of item: "There is a special person who is around when I am in need."		
Measures of health		
Self-rated general health	1	5-point scale
SF-12 mental health score	6	Various
Example of item: "How often during the last four weeks have emotional problems interfered with your normal social activities with family, friends etc.?"		
SF-36 emotional well-being score	5	6-point scale
Example of item: "How often during the last 4 weeks have you felt very nervous?"		

had too many missing values for imputation to be reasonable, so we used data without imputation for this ANCOVA. All other variables had between 0 and 2 missing values. As the items of the Berlin Social Support Scale displayed only minimal variance, they were removed from the dataset before imputation and not used in the study. All descriptive results and figures use non-imputed data.

We used ANCOVA models with the outcome at t2 (e.g. self-rated general health) as the dependent variable, the treatment dummy as independent variable and the outcome variable at t1 as a covariate. ANCOVA is a statistical model which estimates whether the change in a variable (e.g. general health) from t1 to t2 is associated to the treatment (i.e. loss of garden). Regarding model assumptions, we tested normality of the dependent variable using a Shapiro-Wilk normality test, homogeneity of variances using Levene's test, homogeneity of regression slopes by checking whether the interaction term between the covariate and the treatment dummy was significant and independence of the covariate from the treatment dummy with t- or Wilcoxon signed-rank (WSR) tests. For a dataset of the size we are using, violating the normality assumption should not introduce bias to the results (Wooldrige, 2003:171–173). However, where the assumption of homogeneity of regression slopes was violated, we calculated a robust ANCOVA model instead, using the R package WRS2 (Mair and Wilcox, 2020). This model compares trimmed means at selected values of the covariate.

3. Results

In this section we first present our results from the qualitative analysis regarding the experience of imminent eviction (3.1), followed by descriptive quantitative results regarding views on eviction (3.2). Then we present results from the ANCOVA models testing effects of garden loss on social networks (3.3) and on health and well-being (3.4).

3.1. Experience of imminent eviction

The allotment gardeners we met in the field expressed negative emotions regarding the imminent destruction of the gardens. This is evident both in the qualitative and the quantitative analyses. The qualitative analysis shows that gardeners experienced feelings of grief, anger, indignation and powerlessness alongside making do and a pragmatic attitude towards garden loss.

3.1.1. Loss and grief

Gardeners framed the loss of the garden as a loss on different levels. On one level this was a loss of the money, time and effort they had invested over the years. Financial investments in their cabins were lost which is particularly painful if these were recent. The following excerpt illustrates this and gives an idea of the effort that has been put into making the cabin comfortable.

He says that it's very bad for them [gardener and his wife], that the stadium will be built. They've had their garden [and cabin] for 20 years. [...] He says they just did everything up. He shows me the cabin, it's quite big, decorated walls, laminate flooring. I say they are probably here in winter too. He says yes, they have a gas oven. Everything is new, the metal framing for the pergola. Now they have to leave, it's awful for them. (gardener (e), field notes 18.8.2018)¹

Another gardener who successfully grew a large variety of vegetables and fruit and said how he enjoyed just watching plants grow referred to an emotional loss. Losing the garden would be losing access to his own green space and his connection to farming, which was emotionally important to him.

¹ (e) refers to gardeners who were to be evicted, (r) to gardeners who could remain.

“He says if he lost the garden, he would be losing something very important, not in an economic sense but emotionally. [...] It’s not that he doesn’t have enough to do. He grew up with farming, he needs green.” (gardener (r), field notes 11.9.2018)

Many gardeners’ narratives evoked an emotional dimension, expressing sadness and grief over the loss of the garden. Gardeners spoke about how it “hurt [s]” to give up the garden. The following excerpt puts this in very strong terms:

He asks me into the cabin, shows me the wood paneling inside which he himself did, as an apprentice decades ago. He says he wants to be present when the bulldozers flatten his hut, which belonged to his father before being passed on to him. “It [the destruction of the garden] is like being present when someone dies, he said, it’s a very strong emotion. [...] There are so many memories here”. (gardener (e), field notes 22.8.2018)

Here the loss of the garden is an experience akin to the death of a loved one. More generally, many gardeners evoked their personal and family history when talking of the loss of the garden. Some gardeners had had their garden for decades, their children had grown up here, some of them had even inherited the garden from their own parents. The gardens were “family gardens” in an emphatic sense of the word, they were places linked to countless memories and to family histories. The cabins, the gardens, certain trees all carried important memories, e.g. of past pleasures and loved ones who have passed away. The gardens were the outcome of common efforts, of projects initiated decades earlier. Several gardeners talked of “saying goodbye” to their gardens, a difficult task. The mourning of the imminent loss of the garden was thus also a mourning of the loss of a place rich in memories.

3.1.2. Anger and injustice

In the interviews and field conversations many gardeners expressed anger and indignation about the imminent loss of their garden. The following excerpt from the field notes illustrates this gardener’s strong emotional reaction to the loss of his garden.

“The gardener is talking and talking and is very upset which I find difficult to cope with. He is very angry that his garden will be cleared. He had inquired if he could get another garden within the association but after being offered a garden, someone else got it. He thinks the responsible people are corrupt.” (gardener (e), field notes 18.8.2018)

The gardener suspected foul play in regard to the allocation of gardens, giving his anger a focus. Many gardeners were also angry about the clearance fee of 250 CHF they had to pay if they left the cabin standing on their allotment. If they returned the allotment as a plot of bare land the fee was not charged, but this would have required a great effort to clear the allotment.

What angers him, he says, is that he will have to pay. How is that supposed to add up? They take something from you and then you have to pay as well? That doesn’t add up, not mathematically, not financially, not psychologically. What kind of business is that? [where] someone comes along and says “Mister, I like your watch. I’m going to take your watch and then you have to give me 20 CHF?” (gardener (e), field notes 22.9.2018)

As the excerpt illustrates, the clearing fee was seen as unjust as it seemed as if the city was asking for the gardeners to pay for the fact that they were losing their garden.

3.1.3. Powerlessness

A further recurrent topos in the material can be conceived of as a feeling of powerlessness. The city and the people developing the stadium were indifferent to the protests and interest of the gardeners.

He says they protested vehemently at the annual meeting [of the allotment association], but the representatives of the city and the icehockey club couldn’t have cared less. People [gardeners] cried, people had tears in

their eyes, they’d had the garden for 40 years, what can they do? (gardener (e), field notes 7.8.2018)

The gardeners perceived themselves as small and weak compared with the city and the investors. Their protests were futile, their actions had no effect. This was expressed in a number of metaphors, with gardeners referring to themselves as “worms”, “mice”, “the rank and file” or “the small ones”.

He says he’s just a little mouse. He smiles, holds his thumb and index finger in front of his face, indicating the size of the little mouse. He can’t make a difference, the decisions have been taken. When the big cat comes along, the mouse can’t do anything. (gardener (r), field notes 23.9.2018)

Several gardeners recounted how years and decades ago they had resisted plans to clear the allotment area for development, but that they had not had the energy this time.

3.1.4. Making do with a difficult situation

While the topoi reconstructed so far were clearly negative reactions to the construction of the stadium, there were also other voices which were somewhat more positive towards the construction of the stadium.

He sees it as a good thing that there will be a spot for the ZSC [the ice hockey club whose home stadium will be built]. Greenspaces are important but there are other greenspaces. (gardener (e), field notes 13.9.2018)

These gardeners did not express such strong negative emotions as others, though they did tend to see the loss of the garden negatively. They looked forward either to a time without a garden or to a new garden which they had already started to design in their mind’s eye. One gardener said it was a good time for her to give up the garden, with her children turned teenagers and her business becoming more demanding.

3.2. Views on eviction

A descriptive analysis of the variables measuring views on eviction in the quantitative questionnaire tells a similar story. Among the gardeners in the treatment group, 89% “strongly agreed” (on a 5-point scale of dis/agreement) with the statement “I’m angry that allotment gardeners are being evicted because of the stadium”, while 64% of the control group were of the same opinion. Only 9% of the whole sample stated they strongly disagreed with this statement. Asked whether it was right to build the stadium here, 92% of gardeners in the treatment group strongly disagreed, as did 81% of the gardeners in the control group. There were no significant differences between the treatment and control groups on these two items, as t-tests of the groups means showed (item “angry” $p = 0.09$, $n = 56$; item “right to build” $p = 0.13$, $n = 53$). Finally, 90% of gardeners in the treatment group strongly agreed that losing their garden meant losing something important in their lives (not answered by control sample, $n = 28$).

3.3. Social networks

3.3.1. Number of close garden contacts

Our quantitative data show that allotment gardeners who participated in the survey had varying levels of contact with other allotment gardeners in the Vulkan area. Before eviction, 60% of participants in the control group were in close contact with more than 10 other gardeners in the area, while 10% reported having no close contacts (see Fig. 1). Post-eviction, the proportion of participants in the control group with more than 10 close contacts dropped to 40%, but the overall frequency distribution of close contacts remained similar to before the eviction. Among the treatment group, 40% had more than 10 close contacts before eviction, while 5% reported having no close contacts at all. After eviction, the frequency distribution in the treatment group was inverted: the number of participants in the treatment group with more than 10

Fig. 1. Number of close contacts with other allotment gardeners (t1: n = 44, t2: n = 45).

close contacts had dropped to 15%, while the proportion of those with no close contacts had increased 8-fold to 40%. While the overall picture was more stable within the control group, there was a marked decrease in the proportion of gardeners who had more than 10 close contacts.

To test the effect of treatment with ANCOVA, we first transformed the ordinal contact variable into an approximate metric variable (with the values 0 for '0', 1 for '1', 2 for '2', 4 for the category '3-5', 8 for the category '6-10' and 12 for the category 'more than 10 contacts'). All model assumptions for ANCOVA were met, apart from the normal distribution of the number of close contacts at t2 ($W = 0.832$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$). In a standard ANCOVA using imputed data the covariate, that is the number of close garden contacts at t1, was significantly related to number of close garden contacts at t2 ($F(1, 41) = 35.4$, $p < 0.001$). The effect of eviction after controlling for the effect of the number of close garden contacts at t1 was significant ($F(1, 41) = 4.8$, $p = 0.035$), suggesting a possible causal association between eviction and number of close garden contacts.

3.3.2. Perceived support from other gardeners

The perceived support of other gardeners (see Fig. 2) at t1 was 14.5 in the control group and 14.4 in the treatment group (on a 20-point scale, see Section 2.7). This difference was not significant according to a WSR test used due to non-normality of the variable ($W=235$, $p = 0.8725$, $n = 43$). Perceived support decreased in both groups from t1 to t2, but more so in the treatment group. At t2 perceived support was 12.4 in the control group and 10.7 in the treatment group, a difference which is equally not significant ($W=296$, $p = 0.3017$, $n = 45$).

For ANCOVA all model assumptions were met, apart from the normal distribution of perceived support at t2 ($W = 0.928$, $p\text{-value} = 0.008$, $n = 45$). In a standard ANCOVA (using imputed data) the covariate, i.e. perceived support at t1, was significantly related to perceived support at t2 ($F(1, 41) = 5.5$, $p = 0.024$). However, the effect of eviction was not significant after controlling for the effect of perceived support at t1 ($F(1, 41) = 1.5$, $p = 0.228$).

Fig. 2. Perceived support from other gardeners in Vulkan at t1 and t2 in both groups. The boxplots in Fig. 2 to Fig. 5 show the distribution of the variables at t1 and t2 for both groups. The bold line corresponds to the median, the top and bottom edges of the boxes to the 25 and 75 percentiles and the vertical lines extend 1.5 of an interquartile range from the edge of the box. Separate black dots show outliers.

3.4. Health and well-being

3.4.1. General self-rated health

The mean self-rated general health of participants (see Fig. 3) at t1 was 3.44 in the control group and 3.35 in the treatment group (on a scale of 1–5). This difference was not significant according to a WSR test used due to non-normality of the variable ($W=261$, $p = 0.7898$, $n = 45$). General perceived health dropped in both groups from t1 to t2, but more so in the treatment group. At t2 the mean was 3.24 in the control group and 2.9 in the treatment group, a difference which is not significant either ($W=296$, $p = 0.2734$, $n = 45$).

For ANCOVA all model assumptions were met, apart from the normal distribution of general self-rated health at t2 ($W = 0.899$, p -value < 0.001). Thus, we ran a standard ANCOVA model. There was no difference between the imputed and non-imputed data here, as these variables had no missings. The covariate, general self-rated health at t1, was significantly related to general self-rated health at t2 ($F(1, 41) = 24.2$, $p < 0.001$), but there was no significant effect of eviction on general self-rated health at t2 after controlling for the effect of general self-rated health t1 (ANCOVA: $F(1, 41) = 1.4$, $p = 0.236$).

3.4.2. Mental health score

The mean SF-12 mental health score (range 1–100) at t1 was 52 for the control group and 49 for the treatment group, a non-significant difference ($W=209$, $p = 0.6071$, $n = 39$). At t2 it was 52 in the control group and 48 in the treatment group (not significant, $W=229$, $p = 0.2793$, $n = 39$; see Fig. 4). The mental health score dropped slightly in the treatment group from t1 to t2, while the mean for the control group remained the same.

For ANCOVA all model assumptions were met, apart from the normal distribution of the mental health score at t2 ($W = 0.863$, p -value < 0.001). We ran a standard ANCOVA model using the non-imputed dataset ($n = 39$). In ANCOVA, the covariate (the mental health score at t1) was significantly related to the mental health score at t2 ($F(1, 34) = 20.3$, $p < 0.001$), but there was no significant effect of eviction on the mental health score at t2 after controlling for the effect of mental health at t1 ($F(1, 34) = 1.148$, $p = 0.291$).

3.4.3. Emotional well-being

The mean of the SF-36 emotional well-being score (range 1–100) at t1 was 77 for the control group and 69 for the treatment group, a non-significant difference ($W=331$, $p = 0.0639$, $n = 43$; see Fig. 5). At t2 it

was 75 in the control group and 67 in the treatment group (not significant, $W=319$, $p = 0.1168$, $n = 43$).

For ANCOVA (using the imputed dataset) some model assumptions were met, not however the normal distribution of the mental health score at t2 ($W = 0.935$, p -value $= 0.0146$, $n = 45$) nor the homogeneity of regression slopes (interaction term: $F(1,41) = 5.57$, $p = 0.0231$, $n = 45$). Due to the non-homogeneity of regression slopes we calculated a robust ANCOVA model. The model suggested a significant effect of the treatment variable eviction. Differences in means at three design points were significant or in the last case almost significant on a 5% level (t statistic $= 3.333$, $p = 0.0034$ at emotional well-being =76, t statistic $= 2.880$, $p = 0.0121$ at emotional well-being =80 and t statistic $= 2.129$, $p = 0.0521$ at emotional well-being =84). This suggests a possible causal association between eviction and emotional well-being.

3.5. Summary of results

Our qualitative and descriptive quantitative results show the lived experience of garden loss to be clearly negative for most gardeners. The inferential ANCOVA models do show statistically significant negative effects of eviction on close social contacts in the garden and on emotional well-being, but there is no evidence for effects on perceived social support, self-rated general health or the SF-12 mental health score.

4. Discussion

Utilizing a natural experiment potentially has huge methodological advantages. Despite this, our natural experiment does not display such clear negative psycho-social effects of eviction from an allotment garden as some well-designed studies on psycho-social effects of repossession or eviction from homes (e.g. Hoke and Boen, 2021, McLaughlin et al., 2012, Pevalin, 2009). One plausible reason for this may be that on average, people's homes are more existentially and emotionally important to them than their allotment gardens. However, our data and particularly the qualitative analysis do show that gardeners experienced considerable negative emotions due to the (pending) eviction, leading us to ask if methodological issues regarding the design of the natural experiment could have prevented us from detecting more effects. We discuss our qualitative results and the parallels with residential evictions in 4.1, while we consider methodological limitations, particularly of the natural experiment, in 4.2.

Fig. 3. General self-rated health at t1 and t2 in both groups.

Fig. 4. SF-12 mental health score at t1 and t2 for both groups (y-axis truncated).

Fig. 5. SF-36 emotional well-being score at t1 and t2 for both groups (y-axis truncated).

4.1. Eviction from the garden: emotional distress and loss of urban space

Our qualitative and quantitative results regarding the gardeners' subjective experience of the eviction are the most conclusive. The analysis of qualitative material shows that the lived experience of imminent eviction from the allotment is a negative and often distressing experience for many gardeners. The descriptive quantitative data (Section 3.2) not only confirms the qualitative analysis, but also shows how widespread negative experiences regarding garden loss were among the sample.

In many ways the experience of garden eviction is similar to that of eviction from or repossession of a home. As in our own findings, previous research shows the loss of the home is an intensely emotional experience associated with feelings of anger and helplessness (Collins and Berg, 2019: 1847–1849, Nettleton and Burrows, 2000: 469–470). The comparison of the loss with the death of a loved one (see 3.1.1) is also reported in qualitative research on home loss (Collins and Berg, 2019: 1848–1849, Nettleton and Burrows, 2000: 469). Other aspects of

the experience of the loss of the home, however, find no echo in our findings on garden loss, such as feelings of shame and embarrassment and of loss as a personal failure (Collins and Berg, 2019: 1842–1843, Nettleton and Burrows, 2000: 474–476). Nor is garden loss associated with financial failure, serious indebtedness or homelessness and the corresponding central aspects of social status and the self, as repossession or eviction from a home may be. So while garden loss can be deeply distressing and is experienced in ways very similar to loss of a home, it generally will not engender the same levels of ontological insecurity as loss of a home (McCormack, 2012: 423, 434; Nettleton and Burrows, 2000: 477–478).

We also identify effects which may be relevant on the level of the neighborhood. Our results regarding social contacts indicate that eviction from a garden is associated with the disintegration of a part of the social network of the gardener. The result that 35% of the treatment group lost all close contacts with other allotment gardeners corresponds with statements several participants made during the second survey wave in that they had not visited the allotment area even once since

losing their garden (Field notes 4.9.2019, 7.12.2019). This suggests that many garden contacts are anchored to the social space of the garden. Allotment gardens can be viewed as a kind of *third space* (Thompson, 2018) which facilitates relatively weak social contacts which are however important for the people involved and cannot be easily transferred to other spaces. The negative effects of garden loss thus potentially fray the social fabric of the affected urban neighborhood in a broader sense.

All three health and well-being measures we used – self-rated general health, the SF-12 mental health sum score and the SF-36 emotional well-being score – showed a reduction in values at t2 for the treatment group. The inferential models did not suggest effects on general health or mental health in a broad sense, in contrast to studies on eviction from the home (Hoke and Boen, 2021; Vásquez-Vera et al., 2016; Cannuscio et al., 2012; Pevalin, 2009). However, our analyses do suggest a negative effect of eviction on emotional well-being. This sits well with the qualitative and descriptive results discussed above, suggesting that a negative effect of garden eviction on emotional well-being can be considered a robust result of our study. The negative emotions experienced in relation to the eviction, i.e. anger, grief and perceived powerlessness, are known to be precursors of depression, mediated by stress (Van Praag, 2004) or a perception of social defeat (Patel et al., 2018).

4.2. Limitations of the study

4.2.1. Limitations of the qualitative analysis

Our qualitative material has its limitations. It must be interpreted in relation to the context it was collected in, i.e. a quantitative survey on health and well-being in relation to the pending eviction. This set an interpretative frame which respondents reacted to, as opposed to a more neutral entry we could have used in a purely qualitative study. For example, this may mean respondents spoke more of the pains of eviction than if they had been approached differently.

4.2.2. Limitations of the natural experiment

A methodological issue influencing our quantitative results could be the design of the natural experiment. A major advantage of a natural experiment is that it offers a “treatment” (in our case eviction) which would be difficult to examine with hypothetical questions or a planned experiment. It also has advantages compared to a survey of people evicted *individually* from different garden areas, as it (ideally) ensures a randomization of treatments to participants. Nonetheless, the non-significant results on general health and the broad mental health measure may be because of limitations of our design. Four methodological factors may have reduced the ability of our natural experiment to detect effects: non-equal expectation of groups, contamination of the treatment-control contrast, cross-over and failed randomization (see Murnane and Willett, 2011). As we discuss below, these factors are connected to the real-world processes of (garden) eviction which makes it challenging to avoid them.

The first factor, non-equality in expectation, may be relevant for our results regarding social contacts. While the loss of close contacts with other gardeners is a clear result, one could have expected it to be clearer. A reason may be that gardeners in the treatment group had already lost many garden contacts *prior* to the first survey. As Fig. 1 shows, fewer gardeners in the treatment group reported high numbers of close contacts than in the control group during the first wave. Many neighbors of the gardeners in the treatment group had already given up their garden by the time the first wave of the survey took place. If one assumes that allotment gardeners have most of their close contacts with gardeners in gardens which are close by, it is particularly probable that the widespread early abandonment of gardens meant the remaining gardeners had already lost contacts. If true, this means our two groups are not “equal in expectation prior to treatment” (Murnane and Willett, 2011:137), which would be a condition for drawing causal inference.

The same may also apply to the general and mental health measures. A reason for the lack of any effect of eviction could be that (mental)

health had already deteriorated before t1, introducing a similar inequality in expectations prior to treatment. As Pevalin (2009) shows in a panel study from the UK, evicted home renters are more likely than the general population to show symptoms of common mental illnesses immediately *before* eviction. The emotional strain of the loss takes its toll before eviction. In our case this is plausible, as the gardeners knew in advance that they would lose their garden and reported negative emotions about the eviction.

A second factor interfering with our natural experiment could be contamination, particularly for the effects of eviction on numbers of close contacts and perceived social support. The number of contacts reported dropped from t1 to t2 not only in the treatment group, but also, rather unexpectedly, in the control group. This could be because some gardeners in the control group had close contacts with gardeners who were evicted (but had not abandoned their gardens early) and then lost those contacts by t2. This is a “contamination of the treatment-control contrast” (Murnane and Willett, 2011:70). This same mechanism may also have been at work for the social support variable, as not only the treatment group had a reason to expect less support from fellow gardeners at t2 but also the control group, as the number of contacts had decreased in both groups.

Thirdly, the absence of significant effects could also be due to how gardeners coped with their situation. As mentioned, some of the gardeners in the treatment group had moved to a new garden by t2, so while they had experienced the stress of eviction, the fact they had a new garden may have attenuated negative effects. This is what Murnane and Willett refer to as a “cross-over” (2011:70).

Finally, a reason for absent effects could be a non-random selection process among the treatment group. The gardeners who had abandoned their gardens – and were thus unavailable for the study at t1 – may have experienced the pending eviction as more stressful, leading them to give up the garden earlier. Each of these four factors, if present, would mean our data underestimates the effect of losing the garden on evicted gardeners’ social networks, social support and general and mental health.

5. Conclusions

In this paper we present some evidence of negative psycho-social effects of eviction from an allotment garden. The qualitative and quantitative results regarding the subjective experience of eviction were unambiguous, and the inferential models suggest negative effects of eviction on social contacts and emotional well-being. Based on this we can say that a considerable proportion of gardeners evicted from their allotments suffered some negative psycho-social effects. As garden clearances are set to continue across Switzerland and Europe, we draw two sets of conclusions from our results, one methodological, one substantial.

In a methodological perspective, our study highlights some of the difficulties of designing a natural experiment for this field of research. Our design could have been improved by conducting the first survey wave earlier. Two years before clearance of the gardens rather than one, emotional strain would have been weaker and the abandonment of gardens would not yet have set in, making random sampling possible in the clearance area and (almost) eliminating the problem of sub samples not being equal in regard to expectation prior to treatment. To make this feasible, researchers would have to be (made) aware of planning processes at a very early stage and have funds to conduct studies, even when a clearance decision is not final yet. Also, using gardeners from a different, though nearby allotment area as the control group could reduce the problem of contamination of the control-treatment contrast. If successfully conducted, this kind of study could quantify effects of evictions more reliably.

Turning to substantial issues, we suggest that planning authorities need to view garden clearances as a serious hardship for many of the gardeners affected. The potential negative effects on the social networks and emotional well-being of hundreds of residents of a neighborhood

should also be of interest to neighborhood social services, especially where many of the people affected belong to underprivileged social classes. While losing a home to eviction generally will have greater negative psycho-social effects than losing an allotment garden, gardens are important social spaces for their users, providing them with a space for leisure and belonging. The importance of these spaces may well be greater for the aging and socially underprivileged populations who often use allotment gardens. The importance of the humble allotment garden in weaving the social fabric of the city and sustaining the well-being of some of its residents should not be underestimated.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Christopher Young: Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Nicole Bauer:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

Acknowledgements

Our thanks go to the many gardeners who participated in our study and shared their views with us; to the Familiengartenverein Altstetten-Albisrieden, its president Adolf Gloor, Flavio Cramer, who was responsible for the garden area “Vulkan” and to the patrons of the bistro on the grounds; to Rebecca Baumgartner, Saada Elabed, Florence Favre, Bruno Lips and Loredana Martignetti for their great effort in collecting data and to the two anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments. The project was funded by the Stiftung Suzanne und Hans Biäsch zur Förderung der Angewandten Psychologie (grant number 2018-06).

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